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School Climate and Students' Academic Performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was designed to examine the relationship between school climate and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. A survey research design was adopted for the study and a sample of 240 respondents was drawn from the population of 600 using Taro Yamane's scientific sampling technique. For the objectives of the study to be achieved, three hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study utilized structured questionnaire and interview as the major instruments for data collection. 240 questionnaires were distributed and 220 were returned. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentage and regression. Results showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between variables of school climate such as safety, school infrastructural facilities, school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. It was recommended that, risk management strategies that will enhance and sustain the safety of students in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should be adopted to improve students' academic performance as well as regular monitoring and evaluation of school infrastructural facilities should be carried out in order to detect dilapidated and harmful facilities which might hinder academic activities and students' academic performance in the Polytechnic.

Keywords: School climate, students' academic performance, safety, infrastructural facilities, school neighborhood.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of school climate in the achievement of students' academic performance cannot be underplayed. This is because school climate is an integral and indispensable component of the teaching and learning process in any educational institution.

School climate comprises of improved infrastructural facilities, staff and students' safety, the quality and character of school neighborhood as well as school life as it relates to norms and values, interpersonal relationships and social interactions, and organizational processes and structures. Freiberg (2019) avers that,

students achieve good and excellent grades in a school climate that is safe and conducive. School climate determines all the learning and teaching done in the school environment. A positive climate can make a school a place where both staff and students want to spend a substantial portion of their time.

It is often said that school climate is to school what personality is to an individual. The climate of school is the average characteristics of the individuals in school, such as lecturers and students' morale. According to (Laerd Statistics 2017) school climate does not only comprises the quality and consistency of interpersonal interactions within the school community that influence students' cognitive, social and psychological development of students but infrastructural facilities of the school. Shochet et al. (2016) believe that, lack of good school neighborhood as well as good infrastructural facilities in school such as constant electricity, clean water source, standard and well-furnished hostels can discourage students' achievement of academic performance in schools. McEvoy and Welker (2020) aver that, school climate may affect many areas within the schools setting, chief among these areas are students' academic performance, and staff and students' safety.

1.2 Statement of the problem

School climate is one of the factors determining students' success at school. It constitutes a very diverse set of factors, including student characteristics, the parameters of the educational process and the specific features of the school and its environment. Several studies in this area emphasize the characteristics of students, improved or poor school infrastructural facilities and the influence of neighborhood in which the school is located. Focus has been also shifted to the qualities of lecturers, teaching methods and the learning process. In many decades, researchers have been increasingly analyzing the daily events that take place in schools. They do not only record the objective - physical indicators of teaching and learning activities, but they also capture social and psychological characteristics - school climate the invisible element of school life that influences all participants.

Though it is assumed that, there is a link between school climate (the degree of students' safety, provision of infrastructural facilities as well as the neighborhood of school) and students' academic performance, it is not known to the researcher whether researches are done in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State relating to school climate and students' academic performance. Hence, the need to contribute to knowledge in this regard. It is against this background that, this study was designed to examine the relationship between school climate and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the relationship between school climate and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Other specific objectives include:

- i. To examine the relationship between safety and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. To examine the relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State
- iii. To examine the relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

1.4 Hypotheses

From the objectives of this study, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. Safety has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Figure1: Model of school climate and students' academic performance

(Researcher, 2022)

A positive school climate is widely known as one of the important factors for positive student outcomes. According to the National School Climate Council (2017), school climate is viewed as the quality and character of school life. This includes the patterns of students, parents and school personnel's experiences of school life and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices and organizational structures. For Ashby and Krug (2018) school climate is viewed as part of the school environment associated with attitudinal and affective dimensions and the belief systems of the school that influence students' cognitive, social, and psychological development. Thus, school climate is reflected in the social interactions in and out of the classroom. Similarly, Ehman, (2018) defines school climate as the atmosphere or ambience of an organization as perceived by its members. This implies that, an organization's climate is reflected in its structures, policies, and practices; the demographics of its membership; the attitudes and values of its members and leaders; and the quality of personal interactions.

According to Kuperminc et al., (2011), high students' academic achievement is associated with high lecturers' commitment or engagement, positive peer norms, an emphasis on group or team cooperation, high level of expectation held by lecturers and administrators, consistency in administering rewards and punishments, consensus over curriculum and discipline, and clearly defined goals and objectives. Climate is referred to as the feeling, character or personality of a formal and informal group features and factors in a work environment. Climate is said to affect efforts geared towards the goal attainment of a school negatively or positively. The climate of a school is said to be close or open. Howard (2015) identified six types of climates prevailing in schools such as open, parental, familiar, autonomous, close and controlled. According to Adeogun and Olisaemeka (2011) a positive school climate is seen as an accessible, co-operative, respectful, pleasant, approachable, supportive and highly motivational interaction among the administrators, lecturers and students. A positive school climate improves students' motivation and achievement. It has a positive impact on the mental and behavioral health of students including contributing to a decrease in risky behavior and depressive symptoms and an increase in feelings of belonging. A negative school climate on the other hand is tied to multiple negative outcomes for students and has been shown to exacerbate harmful behaviors and diminish achievement.

According to Hoy (2019) each school has its own unique climate. The type of climate that prevails in a school is the blend of the behavior of the administrators, lecturers, students and parents in that school. Therefore, climate differs from school to school. Accordingly, Freiberg (2019) suggests that climate is an ever-changing factor in schools. This is because the school administrators may choose on specific occasions to adapt different leadership style, which may have a huge impact on the climate that will lead to a change. Consequently, school climate comprises of value, attitude of stake holders, style of leadership and job satisfaction. Positive school climate play significant value for school's effectiveness and closed school climate (schools with uncommitted leaders, unproductive, unsafe, and unhealthy schools) has negative impact on school effectiveness.

The school climate influences student achievement through students' attachment, commitment, involvement and most importantly, through the schools' resources and climate (Freiberg, 2019). The author views school climate as a relatively stable aspect of the school environment. This climate comprises internal characteristics commonly referred to as the quality of interpersonal relations between

students and lecturers, the extent to which a school is perceived as safe and caring place, the degree to which students, parents and staff are involved in collaborative decision making and the degree to which there are high expectations for student learning (Freiberg, 2019). Alternatively, Franco (2010) reports that, school climate refers to the intangibles that can affect the feelings and attitude of the students, lecturers, staff and parents and it comprises the physical and psychological aspect of a school that prove the environment necessary for teaching and learning to take place.

2.2 Safety

The climate of a school has always been and continues to be essential to a schools' success in educating their students and preparing them for a life beyond their environment. Therefore, a school that acknowledges the complexity inherent in its climate and takes clear and conscious steps toward creating one conducive to learning is a school that will inevitably adjudged to be safer school. According to Noddings (2016) if there is a common thread to creating a positive and safe school climate, it is the importance of relationships—student to student and teacher to student. The author believes that the development of strong and sustainable relationships will contribute more to a healthy and safe school than metal detectors ever will, and our ability to teach our students how to develop supportive relationships of their own is as essential a skill as mathematics and reading. According to Hoy (2019) a good, safe or conducive school climate can provide support or encouragement to both staff and students to perform various activities according to their respective duties and functions. Similarly, Freiberg (2019) avers that, students achieve good and excellent grades in a school climate is safe and conducive. The author describes a safe and conducive school climate as one that is free from violence, bullying and disruptive behaviors.

Daryanto & Tarno (2015) opine that, students' achievement is influenced by many factors such as safe and conducive environment, learning style and facilities available. Moos argues that a conducive social climate in schools has a great influence on the learning satisfaction and academic performance. The authors opine that, the opposite of the above several factors can affect students' academic performance negatively. Safety of school environment and conducive classroom climate could encourage students to learn well in school and could improve their performance and achievement of learning outcomes (Omemu, 2018). The author believes that, a conducive climate and environment will provide a sense of security, comfort, freedom and satisfaction both for teachers and students to perform activities in accordance with their respective functions. Supardi (2013) describes a safe school climate as one that is replete with discipline.

2.3 School Infrastructural Facilities

Some of the factors determining student success at school are better and quality infrastructural facilities. According to (Shochet et al. 2016) these factors include standard and well-furnished laboratories, libraries and classrooms. The authors assert that, lack of good infrastructural facilities in school such as constant electricity, clean water source, standard and well-furnished hostels to mention but a few can discourage students' achievement of academic performance in schools. Several other studies shift their focus to the quality of recreational facilities, sport complexes, good road network and uninterrupted internet services in school environment as factors that could encourage and discourage students' academic performance (Kasatkina and Aksenova 2013). These studies do not only record the objective indicators of learning activities within school climate, but they also capture social and psychological characteristics of the school. Thus, school infrastructural facilities should be one of the important factors that parents and students should consider when choosing a school for study.

2.4 School Neighborhood

Living in a poor community can place a double burden on students beyond what their individual circumstances would dictate (Jargowsky, 2013). The poor not only face with the burden of insufficient income but the disadvantages of those around them (Kneebone, 2014). Poor neighborhoods are often associated with lower levels of education, higher levels of unemployment, single parent households, as well as other social issues such as violence, Sampson and Wilson, (2015). Consequently, students in these communities may be exposed to limited role models and deal with neighborhood stress. More so, neighborhood poverty may undermine and weaken neighborhood institutions, such as schools (Sampson and Wilson, 2015). Thus, poor neighborhoods create a disadvantage for students due to a concentration of stress

within these areas.

In examining multiple dimensions of neighborhood disadvantage, Ainsworth- Darnell (2019) finds that economic deprivation (a composite of unemployment and poverty level) and positive role models, such as the percentage of college graduates in the neighborhood, were significantly related to student outcomes while racial/ethnic diversity and residential stability were not significant predictors. Leventhal and Brooks-Gunn (2020) find that socio-economic aspects of neighborhoods are most frequently measured as a composite of poverty rate, percentage of residents with a high school or college degree, percentage of female-headed households, and unemployment rate. Elliott et al. (2016) argue that while poverty concentration is a central characteristic of neighborhood disadvantage, neighborhood disadvantage is a multidimensional cluster of traits, including unemployment and single-parent homes. Wilson (2020) also emphasizes both the importance of joblessness and the breakdown of the family structure as evidenced by households headed by a single female, that contribute to social issues within areas of concentrated poverty. Disadvantaged neighborhoods have been linked with a range of school outcomes including school dropout, low educational aspiration and low high school graduation rate Rendon, (2014). Many studies identify that, living in a disadvantaged neighborhood had a negative impact on the chances of graduating from high school among a national sample of youth (Wodtke 2011).

2.5 Academic Performance

Academic performance is commonly measured by several indicators such as examination/test scores, students/parents' satisfaction, reduced disruptive behavior, less violence/bullying to mention but a few. But there is no general agreement on how these indicators of performance are best tested or which aspects are most important. Academic performance represents the performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, polytechnics and university. Several studies indicate that students' academic performance is a student's strong performance in a given academic area such as tests or examinations (O'Connor and Wormeli, 2011).

Students' academic achievement therefore is largely identified by a range of statistical indicators, which can be said to be the level of attainment of a student in an examination that is, how a student is able to demonstrate his or her abilities in an examination and in real practical life situations or learning environment. The size, type, age and location of the school have been implicated in students' academic achievement. The size of a school has a very important influence on students' academic achievement. Large student population tends to put more work on the teachers and consequently this is likely to have a negative effect on the academic performance of the students (O'Connor and Wormeli, 2011).

2.6 Theoretical Review

According to David (2009) theories are formulated to explain, predict and help in understanding phenomenon and in many cases to challenge and extend existing knowledge within the limits of the critical bounding assumptions. Accordingly, the relationship between school climate and students' academic performance is buttressed by the following theories:

2.7 Expectancy Theory

Expectancy theory, developed by Victor Harold Vroom in 1964 is based on three perceptions: *expectancy*, *instrumentality*, and *valence*, which, by themselves, can influence an individual's motivation, but together can have a more powerful effect. Expectancy theory holds that one's effort will result in attaining the desired goal. Instrumentality is the belief that if the performance expectation is met, the reward will be received, and Valence refers to the value the individual places on the reward. According to the first perception – expectancy, if teachers do not believe they will be rewarded for success, they will be less likely to make the necessary effort.

Providing clear descriptions of the knowledge and skills that will be rewarded, providing opportunities to acquire and apply the knowledge and skills, and the presence of support and technical assistance, are all things that can positively influence the expectancy perception. Instrumentality, which refers to how strongly a person perceives a connection to be between achieving a goal and to experiencing a positive outcome holds that if lecturers achieve the desired results, they will receive the promised bonus. If

they do not believe the results are obtainable, or that they will truly be compensated for achieving them, they are not likely to be motivated to achieve the goals. This is one of the reasons why the system to measure performance must be both valid and reliable and take into account all of the factors that influence students' achievement. Instrumentality also has a direct relationship on valence, the final perception. Valence in this context refers to value. This refers to whether lecturers value the rewards associated with obtaining the desired goals. In the case of pay-for-performance, will the extra monetary rewards that can be earned motivate lecturers enough to obtain the specific goals set forth for them? Using expectancy theory as a base for this study will explore lecturers' attitudes and perceptions of pay-for-performance systems. It will also identify key attributes of effective pay-for-performance systems.

2.8 Ecological Theory

Ecological theory also known as human ecology is an ecological/system framework developed by Urie Bronfenbrenner in 2007. Ecological theory proposes that one must consider the environmental system in which an individual grows in order to understand his/her development and performance. Bronfenbrenner suggested that the ecological environment consists of a set of nested structures with the innermost level, or microsystem containing the developing individual. According to the proponent of this theory, microsystems are directly experienced by the individual and include settings such as the home, school and neighborhood. Development is then influenced not only by the individual settings but also by the relations between settings, what he defined as the mesosystem. Within the education context, ecological theory states that the extent to which students learn is a function of systems at two levels – the relation between characteristics of the learner and their environment (e.g., home, school, neighborhood) and the relations and interconnections between these environments. These relations, which is described as person - environment and environment-environment relations comprise the ecology of education and is an important and necessary part of educational research because what happens, or does not happen, within the educational settings is largely dependent on other ecological spheres. Practically, this theory is however, in agreement with the assumption that, students' academic achievement is influenced by social interactions and other activities within and around school environment.

2.9 Empirical Review

This section would look at the previous studies on school climate and students' academic performance in schools. Omemu (2018) conducted a study to examine the impact of school climate on students' academic performance in Edo State public secondary schools with the population of the study consisted 140 schools in Edo South Senatorial district. The study revealed that, school climate and students' academic achievement are not the same in rural and urban schools, mixed and single schools, large and small school in Edo State. Lukumon, Abraham and Haftamu (2018) carried out a study on effect of school safety on students' academic performance. Case study: Public Secondary School students in Lagos State, Nigeria with a total population of one hundred (100) respondents randomly selected from public schools. The finding of the study showed that public schools do not have effective safety facilities and equipment to take prompt remedial action if security infraction occurs. It was recommended that government should establish and maintain professional relationships with a variety of education stakeholders (including key policymakers and labor leaders) in advancing safety schools.

Aion, Rosmaizura and Zain (2018) carried out a study on the impact of facilities on student's academic achievement in Universiti Malaysia Kelantan, City Campus, Pengkalan Chepa, 16100 Kota Bharu, Kelantan, Malaysia with a total population of 500 students. A structured self-developed questionnaire was designed for the study. The results of the study showed that E-learning of System Management; Teaching Aids and Library of Learning Environment; Hostels, Sports Facilities and Parking and Transportation of Infrastructure were all significant to impact students' academic achievement. Barbara (2011) carried out a study on the effect of school neighborhood on students' performance of schools under Universal Primary Education (UPE) System in Uganda. A Case Study of Wakiso District with population of 100 respondents including teachers, deputy head teachers and head teachers. The finding revealed that teachers' fringe benefits and nature of working conditions greatly affects performance of schools under UPE system.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The survey methods were adopted for this study. It enabled the researcher to elicit information from the sampled population from the field leading to inferences.

3.2 The Study Area

This study was conducted in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Akwa Ibom State is in the South-South zone of Nigeria with its capital at Uyo. The State is the largest oil producing State in Nigeria. The population of the State is estimated at about 309, 573 as of 2006 (NPC, 2006 report). It has land area of 95km² (36. 7sq.ml), Wikipedia encyclopedia (2007). The people in the area are predominantly Ibibio; others include Annang, Oron, Eket, Obolo, Ibeno and other speaking tribes in Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is inhabited by people of different walks of life such as teachers, businessmen, students, traders, civil servants and unemployed youths among others. The choice of this study area was driven by the nearness to the researcher and the relevance of the research topic. The choice of this study area was driven by the relevance of the research topic.

3.3 Population of the study

The population of this study consisted 600 respondents. This covered both ND and HND students of Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa State.

3.4 Sample Size/Technique

Kothari, (2014) defines sample as small group of respondents drawn from a population about which a researcher is interested in getting the information so as to arrive at a conclusion. In this study, a sample of 240 respondents was selected out of 600 respondents because they are considered to represent and have vital information for the study by virtue of their positions. It is assumed that, in research, investigations involving several hundreds or thousands of elements may be practically impossible to collect data from, test, or examine every element. Some believe that, even if it might be possible, it may be prohibitive in terms of time, cost and other human resources. Hence, the reason for selecting this sample size using Taro Yamane scientific formula which is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

N = Population

1 = constant

e = Level of significance

n = sample size

$$n = \frac{600}{1 + 600(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{600}{1+1.5}$$

$$n = \frac{600}{2.5}$$

$$n = 240$$

3.5 Sources of Data Collection

Primary data were obtained through questionnaire and personal interviews with the staff and students of the Polytechnic. The survey method was adopted to enable detailed and independent information not covered by the questionnaire to be expressed by the respondents. Secondary data were obtained from published reports, books, internet, journals, newspapers and magazines.

3.6 Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected through questionnaire titled “School Climate and Students’ Academic Performance Questionnaire (SCSAPQ)” carefully designed and administered to the respondents, as well as through personal interviews. The questionnaire constituted the major instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contained sections A and B. Section A contained personal information about the respondents. Section B contained the main body of the questionnaire. This section contained sixteen (16) close ended questions using a four-point scale instrument through which the opinions of the respondents were expressed. Their responses were measured by means of a four-category rating system as follows:

SA	-	Strongly agree
A	-	Agree
D	-	Disagree
SD	-	Strongly disagree

3.7 Validity of Research Instrument

The validity of the research instrument was assessed by the research supervisor and other research experts in the school of management sciences of the Akwa Ibom State University. These experts assessed the relevance of each item in relation to the objectives of the study, the hypotheses to be tested and language used in developing the items as well as the comprehensibility of each item in relation to the cognitive level of the respondents. They validated the instrument by effecting necessary corrections, examining the contents and ascertaining clarification of ideas as well as appropriateness of the items. The final instrument would be reflected on the appendix.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

In order to determine the reliability of the instrument used in the study, the corrected questionnaire was administered randomly on selected students of Heritage Polytechnic, Eket, Akwa Ibom State. This approach was repeated with the same group after three weeks period and the results obtained from the first and second pre-test were consistent, therefore, the instrument is believed to be reliable.

3.9 Procedure for data Collection/Administration of the Instrument

Data collection was done in the sampled Polytechnic in the study area. The researcher visited the Polytechnic with letter from the supervisor to obtain permission from the school and clarified the motivation behind the study to them. Relevant information for the study was gathered by the researcher with the assistance of the HODs and students’ leaders in each of the departments. The staff and students were informed of the activity and the need to give honest responses to the instructions that data collected would be used and treated confidentially for academic research purposes only. After this, the researcher undertook the administration of the questionnaire to respondents with the help of research assistant in each of the departments used for the study.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Considering the nature of data collected, the statistical methods adopted for data analysis was regression. The data were analyzed with the help of a statistical tool using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

The data presented contain responses to the items in the questionnaire and the computed data for variables of the study. The data on the items are based on the four-point Likert scale used in scoring the instrument.

4.1.1 Data Presentation on Questionnaire Administered

Table 1: Data Presentation on Questionnaire Administered

Questionnaires	Number of questionnaires	Percentage (%)
Total questionnaires served	240	100
Total questionnaires Returned	220	91.67
Total not Returned	15	6.25
Total useful	200	83.33
Total discarded	5	2.08

Source: Field Survey (2022)

In the above Table 1, it was observed that out of the total of 240 questionnaires distributed, 220 questionnaires representing 91.67% were returned, 15 questionnaires representing 6.25% were not returned, 200 correctly and completely filled questionnaires representing 77.82% were used to interpret the results. Only 5 questionnaires representing 2.08%, out of 240 questionnaires distributed, were completely discarded from the analysis.

4.1.2 Data Presentation on Respondents' Demographic

Table 2: Data Presentation on Respondents' Demographics

Demographics	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	110	55
	Male	90	45
	Total	200	100
Age	51 and above	23	11.5
	41 – 50	50	25
	36 – 40	31	15.5
	31- 35	42	21
	21-30	29	14.5
	15-20	25	12.5
	Total	200	100
Marital Status	Widowed	11	5.5
	Divorced	5	2.5
	Separated	45	22.5
	Married	89	44.5
	Singled	50	25
	Total	200	100
Educational Qualification	Ph.D.	5	2.5
	M.Sc./MBA	39	19.5
	HND/B.Sc.	46	23
	OND/NCE	49	24.5
	SSCE	61	30.5
	Total	200	100
Years /level of study	Others	5	2.5
	HNDII	46	23
	HNDI	50	25
	NDII	49	24.5
	NDI	50	25
	Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey Data (2022)

From Table 2, it was observed that a total of 90 respondents representing 45% were male while a total of 110 representing 55% of the respondents were female. This implied that majority of the participants were female. This does not presume the fact that using more women in the study will in any way affect the analysis and findings of the study. This is because the opinions expressed are highly likely to represent general opinion or position concerning the research issues and not depending on feminine or masculine

opinion or position. Also, the majority of the respondents (25%) were under the age bracket between 41 – 50 years. Majority of the respondents 89 (44.5%) were married. Majority of the respondents 50 (25%) have were in ND1 and HND1 respectively.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Safety and students' academic performance

The first objective was on the relationship between safety and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This suggests that respondents were asked several questions linking safety to students' academic performance. The responses are presented in Table 3 and following is the interpretation.

Table 3: Analysis of research constructs on the relationship between safety and students' academic performance

Research Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)
Students' performance is high in a safe and conducive school environment.	98(49%)	53(26.5%)	31(15.5%)	18(9%)
Students' scores in tests and examinations are high in violence free school environment.	83(41.5%)	50(25%)	27(13.5%)	40(20%)
Students feel protected and secured in a safe school climate.	68(34%)	48(24%)	39(19.5%)	45(22.5%)
Students derive both physical and psychological satisfaction in a peaceful school climate.	70(35%)	45(22.5%)	41(20.5%)	44(22%)

Source: Field Survey Data (2022)

Table 3 shows that majority of respondents gave affirmation that students' performance is high in a safe and conducive school environment. This was shown in the 98 respondents representing 49% that strongly agreed to the claim. Also, it was revealed that 83 respondents representing 41.5% strongly agreed that students' scores in tests and examinations are high in violence free school environment. Furthermore, 68 respondents representing 34% strongly agreed that students feel protected and secured in a safe school climate. It was also found that 70 respondents representing 35% strongly agreed that Students derive both physical and psychological satisfaction in a peaceful school climate. Based on these affirmations, it could be averred that respondents' opinion on the items are sufficient to guarantee scientific analysis and a valid conclusion. This indicates that each independent research construct or variable has some kind of relationship with the dependent research construct or variable.

4.2.2 School infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance

The second objective was on the relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This infers that respondents were asked several questions linking school infrastructural facilities to students' academic performance. The responses are presented in Table 4 and following is the interpretation.

Table 4: Analysis of research constructs on school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance

Research Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)
A standard and well – designed classrooms enhance students' academic performance.	45(22.5%)	70(35%)	44(22%)	41(20.5%)
A well-designed recreational facility enhances students' performance.	53(26.5%)	64(32%)	37(18.5%)	46(23%)
Good communication and internet	40(20%)	99(49.5%)	28(14%)	33(16.5%)

network within school environment improve students' academic performance.				
Provision of basic amenities in school environment enhances students' academic performance.	38(19%)	97(48.5%)	33(16.5%)	32(16%)

Source: Field Survey Data (2022)

Table 4 shows that majority of respondents gave affirmation that A standard and well – designed classrooms enhance students' academic performance as evidenced in the 70 respondents representing 35% that agreed to the claim. Also, it was revealed that 64 respondents representing 32% agreed that a well-designed recreational facility enhances students' performance. 99 respondents representing 49.5% agreed that good communication and internet network within school environment improve students' academic performance. It was also found that 97 respondents representing 48.5% agreed that provision of basic amenities in school environment enhances students' academic performance. This finding is subject to scientific testing and until such test is conducted, it becomes valid.

4.2.3 School neighborhood and students' academic performance

The third objective was on the relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This entails that respondents were asked several questions linking school neighborhood to students' academic performance. The responses are presented in Table 5 and following is the interpretation.

Table 5: Analysis of research constructs on school neighborhood and students' academic performance

Research Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	SD (2)	D (1)
Poverty stricken neighborhood influences students' academic performance.	41(20.5%)	96(48%)	32(16%)	31(15.5%)
Neighborhood with antisocial behaviors do not encourage students' academic performance.	100(50%)	78(39%)	17(8.5%)	5(2.5%)
Schools located in a highly expensive environment may discourage students' academic performance.	38(19%)	130(65%)	19(9.5%)	13(6.5%)
Many drop-outs are as a result of disadvantaged neighborhood.	50(25%)	111(55.5%)	15(7.5%)	24(12%)

Source: Field Survey Data (2022)

Table 5 shows that 96 of respondents (48%) gave affirmation by agreeing that poverty-stricken neighborhood influences students' academic performance. Also, it was revealed that 100 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed that Neighborhood with antisocial behaviors do not encourage students' academic performance. Furthermore, 130 respondents representing 65% agreed that schools located in a highly expensive environment may discourage students' academic performance. It was also found that 111 respondents representing 55.5% agreed that many drop-outs are as a result of disadvantaged neighborhood. However, at this level, until statistically and scientifically tested, significant causality can only be assumed but not claimed between each explanatory variable and the explained variable.

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

The first hypothesis (H_{01}) was that: "Safety has no significant relationship with students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State". This hypothesis was tested using simple regression statistics and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Regression Results of Safety on students' academic performance

Dependent Variable <i>Students' academic performance</i>	Coef.	Std. Error	t-stat	p-value
Model Parameters				
Const.	4.075	.154	26.502	.000
Safety	.230	.041	5.660	.000
Model Characteristics				
F-Stat	32.031			
R-Square	.097			
Adj. R ²	.094			
D-W Stat.	2.054			

Source: Researcher's Computation (2022) from SPSS Output.

The test of the null hypothesis (H_0) against the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is that H_0 is rejected if the calculated statistical probability is less than the p-value of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.000 is less than the p-value of 0.05, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, which states that safety has a significant relationship with students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that safety positively and significantly influenced students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

4.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

The second hypothesis (H_{02}) was that: "There is no significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State". This hypothesis was tested using simple regression statistics and the results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Regression Results of school infrastructural facilities on students' academic performance

Dependent Variable <i>Students' academic performance</i>	Coef.	Std. Error	t-stat	p-value
Model Parameters				
Const.	2.786	.200	13.947	.000
School infrastructural facilities	.188	.053	3.575	.000
Model Characteristics				
F-Stat	12.778			
R-Square	.041			
Adj. R ²	.038			
D-W Stat.	1.853			

Source: Researcher's Computation (2022) from SPSS Output.

The test of the null hypothesis (H_0) against the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is that H_0 is rejected if the calculated statistical probability is less than the p-value of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.000 is less than the p-value of 0.05, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis,

which states that there is a significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

4.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

The third hypothesis (H_{03}) was that: "There is no significant relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State". This hypothesis was tested using simple regression statistics and the results are presented in Table 8.

Table 4.8: Regression Results of school neighborhood on students' academic performance

Dependent Variable	Coef.	Std. Error	t-stat	p-value
<i>Students' academic performance</i>				
Model Parameters				
Const.	2.956	.250	11.826	.000
School neighborhood	.172	.067	2.564	.011
Model Characteristics				
F-Stat	6.575			
R-Square	.022			
Adj. R ²	.018			
D-W Stat.	1.891			

Source: Researcher's Computation (2021) from SPSS Output.

The test of the null hypothesis (H_0) against the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is that H_0 is rejected if the calculated statistical probability is less than the p-value of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.011 is less than the p-value of 0.05, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

4.4 Discussion of the Findings

4.4.1 The relationship between safety and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

The results of the regression analysis were presented in Table 6. From the results, the regression coefficient value of 4.075, shows there is a positive relationship between safety and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Also, a regression co-efficient of 0.230 implies that a percentage increase in safety causes about 0.23% increase in students' academic performance. From the results, the R² value is 0.097. This indicates that safety explained only about 9.7% variations in students' academic performance, while the remaining 90.3% may be explained by variables outside the regression model. Since the calculated p-value of 0.000 was less than the p-value of 0.05. The finding was that safety has a significant relationship with students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

4.4.2 The relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The results of the regression analysis were presented in Table 7. From the results, the regression co-efficient value of 2.786, shows there is a positive relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Also, a regression co-efficient of 0.188 implies that a percentage increase in school infrastructural facilities causes about 18.8% increase in students' academic performance. From the results, the R² value is 0.041. This indicates that school

infrastructural facilities explained only about 4.1% variations in students' academic performance, while the remaining 95.9% may be explained by variables outside the regression model. Since the calculated p-value of 0.000 was less than the p-value of 0.05. The finding was that there is a significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

4.4.3 The relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

The results of the regression analysis were presented in Table 8. From the results, the regression co-efficient value of 2.956, shows there is a positive relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Also, a regression co-efficient of 0.172 implies that a percentage increase in school neighborhood causes about 17.2% increase in students' academic performance. From the results, the R^2 value is 0.022. This indicates that school neighborhood explained only about 2.2% variations in students' academic performance, while the remaining 97.8% may be explained by variables outside the regression model. Since the calculated p-value of 0.000 was less than the p-value of 0.05. The finding was that there is a significant relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the findings

The findings of the study are summarized below:

- i. Safety has a significant relationship with students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between school infrastructural facilities and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. There is a significant relationship between school neighborhood and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

5.2 Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between school climate and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. All independent variables were found to have positive and significant influence on the dependent variable used in this study. Based on the findings, the researcher concludes that there is a positive and significant relationship between school climate and students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Risk management strategies that will enhance and sustain the safety of students in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State should be adopted to improve students' academic performance.
- ii. Regular monitoring and evaluation of school infrastructural facilities should be carried out in order to detect dilapidated and harmful facilities, which might hinder academic activities in particular and students' academic performance in general.
- iii. Security operatives should be hired to monitor the school neighborhood to maintain a cordial relationship with the students. This will create peace of mind and boost students' morale for effective students' academic performance in Trinity Polytechnic, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

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APPENDIX I

SCHOOL CLIMATE AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN TRINITY
POLYTECHNIC, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE.

S/N	SAFETY	SA	A	SD	D
A					
6	Students' performance is high in a safe and conducive school environment.				
7	Students' scores in tests and examinations are high in violence free school environment.				
8	Students feel protected and secured in a safe school climate.				
9	Students derive both physical and psychological satisfaction in a peaceful school climate.				
B	SCHOOL INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES				
10	A standard and well – designed classrooms enhance students' academic performance.				
11	A well-designed recreational facility enhances students' performance.				
12	Good communication and internet network within school environment improve students' academic performance.				
13	Provision of basic amenities in school environment enhances students' academic performance.				
C	SCHOOL NEIGHBORHOOD				
14	Poverty stricken neighborhood influences students' academic performance.				
15	Neighborhood with antisocial behaviors do not encourage students' academic performance.				
16	Schools located in a highly expensive environment may discourage students' academic performance.				
17	Many drop-outs are as a result of disadvantaged neighborhood.				
D	ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE				
18	Students' results in Trinity Polytechnic is very good.				
19	There are few cases of students' bully and violence in Trinity Polytechnic.				
20	There are less reduced disruptive behaviors of students in Trinity Polytechnic.				
21	There is high level of parents/students satisfaction in Trinity Polytechnic.				

APPENDIX II

Table 6: Regression Results for Hypothesis One

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.312 ^a	.097	.094	1.0617	2.054

- a. Predictors: (Constant), safety
 b. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.108	1	36.108	32.031	.000 ^b
	Residual	335.928	198	1.127		
	Total	372.037	199			

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), safety

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	4.075	.154		26.502	.000		
	Safety	.230	.041	.312	5.660	.000	1.000	1.000

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

Table 7: Regression Results for Hypothesis Two

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.203 ^a	.041	.038	1.1352	1.853

- a. Predictors: (Constant), school infrastructural facilities
 b. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.468	1	16.468	12.778	.000 ^b
	Residual	384.052	198	1.289		
	Total	400.520	199			

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), school infrastructural facilities

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.786	.200		13.947	.000		
	school infrastructural facilities	.188	.053	.203	3.575	.000	1.000	1.000

- a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

Table 8: Regression Results for Hypothesis Three

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.147 ^a	.022	.018	1.1650	1.891

a. Predictors: (Constant), school neighborhood

b. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.924	1	8.924	6.575	.011 ^b
	Residual	404.463	198	1.357		
	Total	413.387	199			

a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), school neighborhood

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.956	.250		11.826	.000		
	school neighborhood	.172	.067	.147	2.564	.011	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: students' academic performance

Source: Researcher's Computation via SPSS